

FEAST

Report on indicator recommendations

Report

D2.2

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Food systems that support transitions to hEalthy And Sustainable dieTs

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ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Table 2 *List of acronyms and abbreviations*

FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
NCD	Non-Communicable Diseases
SSA	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies
KU LEUVEN	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven

1. Introduction

Our current diets and food systems are major drivers of environmental pollution and resource demand (Springmann et al, 2018), representing a great risk to both our health and to the environment. It is estimated that the hidden costs of global agrifood systems account for approximately 12 trillion USD annually, with 70% of the costs being linked to the health system which must deal with the rising cases of preventable, diet-related non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as cardiovascular diseases and diabetes; the remaining costs stem from agricultural practices that damage the environment through, for example, increased GHG emissions, nitrogen runoff and water pollution (FAO, 2024). In this scenario, the role of individuals and their shift to healthier and more sustainable eating patterns become of crucial importance to shape more sustainable food systems, which contribute positively to both people's health and the environment.

To meet this end, a literature review was conducted within the FEAST project to identify the main barriers and drivers associated with adherence to healthier and more sustainable diets. The results of this literature review were used to design a cross sectional survey that was administrated across 27 EU countries to map the eating patterns and the related food behaviours, including drivers and barriers to healthier and more sustainable diets within the European adult population (Murante et al., 2025). The goal of these activities was to inform policymakers and other stakeholders from the food system about factors affecting the current food behaviour of the population so that more effective and context-sensitive policies and strategies could be designed and implemented to support the transition to healthier and more sustainable eating behaviour in Europe.

The following document introduces the results from the literature review and recommends a list of indicators to monitor the spread or the reduction of the above drivers and barriers across the European population by means of policy, strategies and interventions which target the factors inhibiting or driving healthier and more sustainable food choices in the European population. Additionally, to demonstrate how the indicators can be adapted/adopted for different modalities, a toolkit is presented including examples of strategies and interventions to address drivers and/or barriers to healthier and more sustainable food behaviours. Among other strategies, this toolkit also uses social media as an example medium for communicating messages to support the transition to healthier and more sustainable eating behaviour and also demonstrates how the indicators can be adopted for monitoring purposes.

2. Methodology

The work began with a *literature review* (Kaptejins et al. 2025) on food behaviours to identify factors influencing food choices and to identify the drivers and barriers to adherence to a healthy and sustainable diet. A second *literature review* (Vanwinkelen, et al., 2025) was conducted focused on digital media to understand the role they play in food choices.

Using these results, we created both a list of indicators and a practical toolkit. *The list of indicators* considered the main factors influencing food behaviour to measure the impact over time of strategies implemented with the scope of addressing healthy and sustainable eating habits. Indicators were grouped in 7 categories to create a multidimensional assessment framework.

The *toolkit* "Barriers and drivers of healthy and sustainable eating behaviour", also inspired by behavioural change frameworks and empirical studies, was created to illustrate an example of practical

tools that can be used to promote healthy and sustainable eating habits in Europe. The purpose was to demonstrate how the research findings from the WP2 on barriers and facilitators can be translated into actions that policymakers and other actors in the food system can implement to address the issue at hand.

3. Results

3.1 What influences food choices?

According to Blake et al. (2021), a consumer food choice is defined as “a decision-making process whereby individuals consider, acquire, prepare, distribute and consume foods and beverages.” This process is influenced by several factors at the individual and food environmental levels because consumer food choices do not depend solely on personal preferences based on foods people like and/or individual knowledge or habits, they also depend on the food environment, which determines the accessibility and affordability of food products, thus having a direct impact on the opportunities people have to eat healthier and more sustainable diets. (Kaptejins et al. 2025)

The literature review conducted in the first stage of the FEAST project (Kaptejins et al. 2025) identified the following main groups of drivers and barriers dealing with food consumption behaviour: *Accessibility and Affordability*, *people’s Attitude*, and *Beliefs, Awareness and Ethical Values*, *Family and Social Influence*, and their *Food Preferences* and *Food literacy*. Table 3 provides further details on the groups, including the populations for which drivers and barriers were observed. Below is a summary of the main findings.

Availability and affordability are the two main factors influencing food behaviour based on a person’s income and personal resources. “Higher income typically allows individuals to afford a wider variety of healthy and sustainable options” (Asvatourian et al., 2018; Rosas et al., 2021), while price remains a significant barrier for those with lower incomes. (Bukman et al., 2014) For those with no economic restrictions, accessing healthy and sustainable foods near where they live or work might not pose a problem. But for those with limited financial means and/or a limited number of places to purchase affordable, healthier and more sustainable foods near where they live or work (i.e. in so-called “food deserts” or “food swamps”), long hours of transportation to reach better food options may pose a problem, especially if they are “time poor” (e.g. having long commutes or working multiple jobs). (Kaptejins et al. 2025) The consumption of unhealthy and unsustainable diets by these groups does not represent the preference of most of these groups; for example, if better food options were offered in a way more closely aligned to people’s daily routines – e.g. through community gardens, schools, workplaces, hospitals and other institutions – these groups would be more likely to adhere to healthier and more sustainable diets. (Murante et al., 2025) Aligned with this, a recent Dutch study by Vellinga (2024) demonstrated that even modest dietary changes can improve health and reduce the environmental impact of diets across all socio-economic subgroups, without increasing diet costs. (Kaptejins et al. 2025)

Another set of factors that influence an individual’s food choices are their **attitude and beliefs**. Attitudes and what one chooses to believe can either be a strong driver through self-motivation, self-discipline, willingness and an altruistic concern, or a barrier for those with impulsive behaviour, idleness or lacking motivation and will. (Appleton et al., 2017; Giampetri et al., 2022; Kymäläinen et al., 2021; Li et al., 2021; Pereira et al., 2021; Pinho et al., 2017; Vos et al., 2022) Additionally, the literature

demonstrates that an intention-behaviour gap exists – i.e. good intentions do not necessarily lead to effective behaviours. (Sullivan et al., 2021; Baur et al., 2022) Because eating healthily and more sustainably requires new behaviours (e.g. a change of habit, exploration of new flavours and textures), intentions are necessary but not sufficient to actually lead to the change in behaviour needed for people to shift to better diets. (Sullivan et al., 2021; Baur et al., 2022)

Related to food literacy, **awareness and ethical values** are also important factors that can influence food choices. Awareness to risk (of consuming unhealthy diets), and the value an individual gives to their health and the environment can serve as drivers to eating healthily and more sustainably; although some start caring only after their health has been compromised (Bukman et al., 2024). Generally, there is an interest and an effort in the population for protecting animal welfare and one's overall state of health through better eating habits. (Aksoy et al., 2021; Chang et al., 2021; Giampetri et al., 2021; Grasso et al., 2021; Henn et al., 2022; Howard et al., 2019; Jezewska-Zychowicz & Plichta, 2022; Nestorowicz et al., 2022; Salmen et al., 2021; Žeželj et al., 2012) Similarly, **personal food preferences**, for example food taste, are a strong driver of food choices, but it is important to note that these can also be rooted in biological and cultural factors. On the one hand, there is a human preference for salt, sugar and fat (Drewnowski & Almiron-Roig, 2010; Drewnowski and Greenwood, 1983; Mattes, 1997), precisely the ingredients that are to be controlled to achieve healthier diets. And on the other hand, “taste is a strong determinant” (Steptoe et al. 1995, Renner et al. 2012, Kourouniotis et al. 2016, Bauer et al. 2022, Rejman et al. 2019) and it is usually shaped by culinary culture. In this sense, a person's food preferences become a reflection of their social identity and values. Furthermore, individuals are mostly inclined to follow a habit-based approach to food, prioritizing convenience, which means that individuals tend to be guided by the tastes and eating habits already known to them. (Murante et al., 2025). The challenge is not only to inform the public about the benefits of a healthier and more sustainable diet, but also on reshaping the social and cultural norms of the community.

Linked to cultural factors, **family and social influences** also play an important role in shaping dietary behaviours. Whether it is parents who follow healthy and sustainable eating habits that are passed down to their children, or the influence of friends and peers, social factors can serve as a barrier or facilitator to transitioning to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviours. (Giampetri et al., 2021; Kopetsky et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2021; Pettigrew et al., 2015) Food marketing and media, as well as environmental and ethical trends can also influence dietary behaviours. (Pettigrew et al., 2015; Rosas et al., 2021; Salmen et al., 2021; Vanwinkelen et al., 2025) **Food literacy** is a key driver to support the adherence to healthier and more sustainable diets, as it helps to set the standard on the objectively more nutritious and sustainable dietary options. Food literacy in this case is defined as the level of proficiency in descriptive knowledge and skills related to nutrition and healthy eating which allows for the understanding of the impact of one's food choices on health and the environment (Food Literacy Center; Vidgen & Gallegos, 2014).

This broad concept encompasses knowledge on nutrition, diet and cooking, along with contextual skills like meal planning, all of which are considered drivers to adhere to healthier and more sustainable diets. Notwithstanding, descriptive knowledge itself is not enough to change an individual's eating habits. There is a gap between learning and actually applying the knowledge and skills. While some report that food literacy contributes to easing the transition process to healthier and more sustainable habits, others say that it is their lack of cooking skills and planning skills that stands as a barrier. (Henn et al., 2022; Howard et al., 2019; Jezewska-Zychowicz & Plichta, 2022; Kymäläinen et al., 2021; McMorrow et al., 2016; Varela et al., 2021; Vos et al., 2022) Additionally, the reliability of the source of

information plays a role with some individuals having trouble trusting governmental recommendations on healthy eating (Howard et al, 2019), while others reinforce the gap between science and beliefs assuming the information they believe in as being right even if it does not match with the evidence. (Polleau & Biermann, 2021) Knowledge on the impact of food on health and the environment supports people to take more conscious decisions, given a higher level of awareness on the issue at hand, which contributes to shaping ethical values and attitudes towards healthier and more sustainable diets.

Table 3 Drivers and Barriers to healthier and more sustainable diets (source: Kaptejins et al, 2025)

	Drivers	Barriers
Accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of healthy and sustainable foods (adult > 65) • Healthy food provision (nursing care) (older people) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easily available unhealthy foods; poor availability of fruits and vegetables (adult 18-24yrs) • Exposure to unhealthy foods (parents; mothers)
Affordability		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Price (general population; family and adolescence) • Cost (family and adolescence; parents) • Financial scarcity (adults) • Food insecurity (adult) • Perceived cost (adult 18-24yrs) • Income (adult >65) • Price consciousness (university students 18-25yrs)
Attitude and Beliefs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Willingness and self-motivation (adults >65; adults) • self-efficacy (adult 18-24yrs) • altruistic concern (university students) • Self-discipline (adult 18-24yrs; GenZ) • mood (adults) • Positive attitude towards alternatives (adult >65yrs) • Belief (adult 18-24yrs, adults) • Physical appearance (high school students aged 15-19yrs) • Time management (mothers; undergraduate nursing students 18-49yrs) • Eating attitude (adults) • Authoritative parenting style family and adolescence) • Self-motivation (adults) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of willingness (adult >65, adults 18-54, adults) • Idleness (GenZ) • Lack of motivation (undergraduate nursing students 18-49yrs) • Unhealthy foods advertising (watching TV) (children 5-9yrs, parents) • Beliefs (food myths) (adults) • Poor time management (adult 18-24 yrs, adults; mothers, adults) • Lack of trusted information sources (adult 18-24yrs) • Impulse behaviour (GenZ)
Awareness and Ethical Values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness risk (adults 18-24 yrs, university students) • Health value (adults >65yrs; adults) • Health consciousness (adults 26-55yrs) • Self-awareness (internal regulation) (adults) • Environmental and animal welfare awareness (adults >65yrs) • Awareness of societal impact of meat consumption (adults >65yrs) • Awareness of healthy and sustainable food choices (adults >65yrs, general population) • Ethical Value (adults) • Health complaints (adults) • Perceived health benefits (university students) • Health awareness (adults) 	

<p>Family and Social Influence</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authoritative parenting style**(family and adolescence) • Social Support (undergraduate students 18-49yrs, GenZ) • Family influence (adults) 	
<p>Food Preferences</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Culinary tradition (adults) • Familiarity (adults) • Food acceptance (adults) • Taste (adults; adults >65yrs) • Organic food preference (adults 18-25yrs) • Quality aspect of food (adults 18-25yrs) • Sensory Preferences (adults) • Traditional dietary pattern(adults) • Convenience (adults) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exclusionary diets (to give up certain foods) (adults 18-54yrs) • Ease of consumption of unhealthy foods (due to advertisement processed/ultra processed foods) (parents) • Difficulty in consuming healthy diets (parents) • Advertisement of unhealthy foods (adults, parents) • Antinutritional factor of legumes (digestive issues) (adults, adults >65yrs; parents; adults) • Habits (adults >65yrs) • Sensory Appeal (adults >65yrs, adults) • Familiarity (adults) • Convenience (adults) • Taste (adults)
<p>Food literacy</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutritional knowledge (adults >65yrs, adults 18-25yrs; adults 18-32yrs; GenZ) • Culinary knowledge (adults >65yrs) • Culinary confidence (adults >65yrs) • Contextual skills (meal planning) (adults) • Awareness of product labels (university students) • Perceived health benefits (university students) • Dietary education (older) • Cooking skills (mothers, GenZ) • Parental knowledge (family and adolescence) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of nutritional literacy (adults) • Not clear Information (adults) • Lack of planning skills (GenZ) • Lack of awareness of nutritional value of pulses (adults) • Lack of preparation knowledge/cooking knowledge (adults 18-24yrs; adults; adults 25-60yrs) • Lack of cooking skills (adults; adults 18-24yrs) • Lack of knowledge of skills (parents, adults 18-32yrs) • Lack of knowledge on sustainability (adults) • Lack of a reliable source of information (adults, university students)

3.2 Indicators to assess adherence to healthier and more sustainable diets

Utilising the results of the literature review described in section 3.1, Table 4 lists a set of indicators that can be used to measure progress towards enhancing drivers and overcoming barriers to the factors that influence food choices (see also Table 3). The purpose of these indicators is to support the monitoring of changes in food behaviour over time and to assess the impact of interventions, policies and strategies. Some indicators are designed for specific subgroups of the general population, in line with current evidence.

Table 4 A proposal of indicators to monitor the transition towards healthier and more sustainable diets

	Measures
Accessibility	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Percentage of <i>older people</i> who have access to healthy and sustainable food options in their food environment . 2. Percentage of <i>older people</i> who have access to healthy and sustainable food options in the health facilities (e.g. nursing home) they utilise 3. Percentage of <i>young</i> adults who have access to healthy and sustainable food options in their food environment. 4. Percentage of <i>parents</i> who perceive a high exposure of unhealthy foods in their food environment.
Affordability	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Percentage of young adults who report healthy and sustainable foods as affordable. 6. Percentage of families who find healthy and sustainable foods affordable. 7. Percent of elderly who perceive their income as not enough to afford healthy and sustainable foods.
Attitude and Beliefs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Percentage of people who report that they can find a way to eat healthy and sustainable food in every situation. 9. Percentage of individuals who find the time to buy and prepare healthy and sustainable meals. 10. Percentage of teenagers and young adults who make time to cook and eat healthy and sustainable foods. 11. Percentage of young adults who trust official recommendations on nutrition.
Awareness and Ethical Values	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 12. Percentage of people aware of the health risks of an unhealthy and unsustainable diet. 13. Percentage of people aware of the environmental risks of an unhealthy and unsustainable diet. 14. Percentage of people aware of the health benefits of a healthy and sustainable diet. 15. Percentage of people aware of the environmental benefits of a healthy and sustainable diet.
Family and Social Influence	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 16. Percentage of young generations who receive support from their families/parents to eat healthy and sustainable food. 17. Percentage of adults who receive family support to eat healthy and sustainable food. 18. Percentage of individuals who receive social support to eat healthy and sustainable food.
Food Preferences	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 19. Percentage of people that value traditional culinary practices that support them to eat healthy and sustainable food. 20. Percentage of individuals with a food culture limiting their healthy and sustainable food options. 21. Percentage of people who value food characteristics (sensory, organic nature, quality aspect) to improve the health and sustainability of their diet. 22. Percentage of elderly people open to trying healthy and more sustainable foods.
Food literacy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 23. Percentage of individuals who can identify healthy and sustainable foods. 24. Percentage of individuals who can identify unhealthy and unsustainable foods. 25. Percentage of individuals who know about the nutritional information of foods they consume. 26. Percentage of individuals who know how to prepare healthy and sustainable meals. 27. Percentage of individuals who feel self-effective in preparing healthy and sustainable meals.

3.3 Information sources

An activity conducted in WP2 deals with the exploration of the information sources people use to guide their food choices and how media informs dietary behaviours. In the cross-sectional survey across 27 European countries (D2.1), we found that the second most common source for nutrition information for Europeans is family (51%); mostly for people with low levels of education. Additionally, a large proportion of respondents consult online resources (40%) more frequently than traditional media (32.2%). Consumer-related sources like supermarkets, food labels or food packaging were used by 33.4% of survey respondents. Friends, peers or neighbours were a source of information for 31.5% of respondents, and health professionals were mentioned by 27.6% of respondents. Government

resources and school were used by people the least frequently as a source of information about diets, 11.2% and 7.6%, respectively. Generally, individuals with higher education levels are those who have greater access to diverse food information sources such as traditional media, digital media, and healthcare professionals (Murante et al., 2025).

The above results highlight an important role for both social context (family, friends, peers, neighbours) and online resources in influencing consumer food behaviours. It firstly highlights the importance of supporting “community” food literacy. Through the literature review (Kaptejins et al. (2025), we learned that an increase of nutritional knowledge, culinary knowledge and confidence, as well as awareness of product labels and cooking skills were needed in different subgroups of the population. Aligned with these findings, the WP2 team has developed a toolkit to support food system actors to define strategies and implement interventions to support the drivers and remove the barriers influencing healthy and sustainable diet consumption among different consumer groups (Annex 1).

Secondly, special attention ought to be given to the use of digital media given how pervasive it is. A second literature review has been conducted (Vanwinkelen, et al. 2025), and its results highlight that:

- While digital media can lead to unhealthy dietary habits, it can also be used to effectively enhance healthy and sustainable eating behaviour.
- Subgroup analyses indicated that interventions via social media or text messaging were most effective.
- Interventions incorporated a wide range of behaviour change techniques, with variations in prevalence depending on the type of digital medium used.
- The most promising behaviour change technique was social support and the findings of the narrative review emphasized the effectiveness of communicating social norms.
- Digital media can be a tool to both prevent meat consumption and promote consumption of plant-based foods.
- Digital interventions seem most successful among young adults; there were only a few studies targeting adolescents, making it difficult to draw concrete conclusions for this group.
- Few interventions included or targeted low SES individuals, despite the critical need to reach these populations in order to reduce diet-related health inequalities.

Hence, digital media - especially social media - has the potential to spread health information and promote better eating habits. Considering the number of active accounts on Facebook, Instagram and TikTok, and how much these platforms are embedded into modern life, they can serve as a means of reaching the public with healthy eating campaigns and information regarding the impact of food choices to our health and the environment.

3.4 Toolkit

To accurately address the European population in tackling the barriers and promoting the drivers to support adherence to healthy and sustainable diets, we developed a toolkit, “BARRIERS AND DRIVERS OF HEALTHY AND SUSTAINABLE EATING BEHAVIOR”, to **translate research findings into practical tools that can support the promotion of healthy and sustainable eating behaviors** across Europe. While extensive scientific work has been conducted to identify the drivers and barriers that influence dietary choices, too often this knowledge remains within the research community. As a result, valuable insights are not fully leveraged by those working to support people to change their dietary behaviour. The toolkit aims to bridge this gap. It connects key findings from the WP2 research - including evidence from literature reviews, behavior change frameworks, and empirical studies - with actionable guidance that can be used by professionals and organizations in a variety of contexts. In particular, it offers a

structured overview of the key drivers and barriers of dietary change, together with behavioral change techniques and practical examples of interventions.

This toolkit is designed for:

- **Health professionals:** To implement evidence-based strategies for improving dietary behaviors.
- **Researchers:** To develop and evaluate dietary behavior change interventions.
- **Organizations and policymakers:** To design and implement programs that promote healthy and sustainable eating habits.
- **Food system actors:** To integrate effective communication strategies that encourage better food choices among consumers.

3.4.1 How to read the toolkit

The aim of this toolkit is to offer a **structured overview** of the behavioral determinants that influence food choices - ranging from personal attitudes and knowledge to cultural identity and social norms.

The document is organized around key themes such as **food literacy, awareness, skills, time availability, willpower, and social and cultural influences**. Each section presents both **drivers and barriers, supported by concrete techniques and examples that can be applied in public health campaigns, community initiatives, or educational programs** to drive the transition to healthier and more sustainable eating behaviours.

The toolkit is designed to be quickly and easily consulted based on specific contextual needs, featuring clear visual references to guide navigation and direct links to illustrative case studies for practical inspiration. This modular structure reflects the reality of implementing dietary change interventions, where different users may need to focus on specific barriers, population groups, or behavioural drivers. Rather than prescribing a one-size-fits-all approach, the toolkit allows users to identify and address the determinants most relevant to their target audience or intervention setting, and to draw on tested behaviour change techniques that can be flexibly adapted to diverse contexts.

CULTURAL AND SOCIAL NORMS

Cultural and social norms deeply influence eating behaviors by shaping perceptions of what is acceptable, desirable, or valued in food choices. This chapter explores how to leverage positive cultural drivers while addressing cultural or social barriers that may impede healthier and more sustainable diets.

Figure 1 Example of a content from the toolkit "BARRIERS AND DRIVERS OF HEALTHY AND SUSTAINABLE EATING Behaviour"

4. Conclusion

This document synthesizes the results carried out by task 2.4 in WP2 aiming to support Europe’s food systems to address the challenge of monitoring the transition to opportunities for people to eat more healthily and sustainably as well as their adherence to these better diets. To this end, this report presents a list of indicators that can be used to track progress towards overcoming the barriers and supporting the drivers of transitions to healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour. The indicators can be calculated starting from data collected with a periodical European survey to ensure the use of homogenous methods in the data collection and an effective coordination in the monitoring action. Additionally, we offer a practical and comprehensive toolkit to support food system actors in defining strategies and implementing interventions to support and to overcome the existing drivers and barriers to healthier and more sustainable diets in consumer’s daily food habits.

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Annex 1 – Toolkit: “Barriers and Drivers of Healthy and Sustainable Eating Behaviour.”

BARRIERS AND DRIVERS OF HEALTHY AND SUSTAINABLE EATING BEHAVIOR

TECHNIQUES

Behavior Change Techniques (BCTs) are methods used to support and sustain changes in behavior. They provide a common language and structure for designing effective interventions, making it possible to identify which strategies work best in specific contexts. In this handbook, BCTs are applied to help users translate research on dietary drivers and barriers into practical actions, offering a toolbox of targeted solutions to support healthier and more sustainable eating practices.

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INTRODUCTION

Unhealthy and unsustainable eating behaviors are a major public health and environmental concern. Despite growing awareness, changing dietary habits remains a complex challenge influenced by multiple factors, including cultural norms, socioeconomic conditions, and food environments. Many individuals struggle to adopt and maintain healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviors due to a range of barriers. To effectively promote positive changes in eating habits, it is essential to understand the specific determinants influencing behavior within a given population. This toolkit provides guidance on how to address these determinants using behavior change techniques, offering practical examples and strategies.

PURPOSE

The purpose of this toolkit is to provide practical tools for addressing barriers and enhancing drivers of eating behavior in specific contexts. Grounded in behavioural change techniques, it aims to facilitate healthier and more sustainable dietary habits.

AUDIENCE

This toolkit is designed for:

- **Health professionals:** To implement evidence-based strategies for improving dietary behaviors.
- **Researchers:** To develop and evaluate dietary behavior change interventions .
- **Organizations and policymakers:** To design and implement programs that promote healthier and more sustainable eating habits.
- **Food system actors:** To integrate effective communication strategies that encourage better food choices among consumers.

OVERVIEW OF DRIVERS AND BARRIERS

To effectively promote healthy and sustainable eating behaviors, it is essential to understand the factors that influence food choices. These factors can be categorized into drivers (which encourage positive eating behaviors) and barriers (which hinder them). Identifying these determinants helps in designing targeted interventions for specific audiences. Right is an overview of key categories of drivers and barriers, identified through a literature review.

- Food Literacy
- Awareness and Ethical Values
- **Skills, Facilities, and Confidence**
- Time Availability
- Attitude and Beliefs
- Cultural and Social Norms
- Family and Social Support
- Willpower
- Cultural Food Practices and Cultural Identity

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FOOD LITERACY

This chapter explores how food literacy - including nutritional knowledge and skills related to food preparation - shapes people's ability to make healthy and sustainable dietary choices. It highlights common barriers such as lack of knowledge and limited skills, and suggests behavior change techniques to enhance food literacy across different population groups.

DRIVERS

- **Knowledge:**
Nutritional knowledge
Knowledge of preparation

BARRIERS

- **Lack of knowledge**

TECHNIQUES

Strategy

Actions and selected examples

01. Instruction on how to perform the behavior

Personal | Cooking workshops, TV, Social media

- **Social media tutorials (easy and healthy recipes), infographics on how to make a balanced shopping list or a healthy meal.**
- **TV or social media campaign featuring chefs demonstrating easy, affordable plant-based recipes.**
- **A municipal initiative that organizes cooking workshops for low-SES households on how to prepare nutritious meals on a budget.**

02. Feedback on behavior

Personal | App, Dashboard, Chatbot

- **Apps: MyfitnessPal gives real time feedback on calorie – Intake, nutrients and portion size, supermarket: discount on healthy foods combined with feedback: "80% of your foods were healthy!")**
- **A chatbot in a messaging app that analyzes users' food logs and sends encouragement for sustainable choices.**
- **A public dashboard where people from the municipality can track their contributions to environmental sustainability through food choices.**

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03. Information about health consequences

Personal | Video, Social media

- **A YouTube channel featuring expert interviews on how plant-based diets improve overall health.**
- **Social media posts highlighting nutritional benefits of different vegetables and fruits.**

04. Information about social and environmental consequences (1)

Group | Classes

- **Eco-score Educational Initiatives such as offering classes in schools about the impact of food on climate change.**

05. Reward (outcome)(2)

Group | Cooking workshops, Rewards

- **A local government initiative where participants who engage in challenges get free cooking workshops with celebrity chefs.**
- **A reward system in schools where classes have a collective sustainable goal and when it's met, they have a field trip to urban farms.**

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AWARENESS AND ETHICAL VALUES

Awareness of the health and environmental impacts of food choices, along with personal ethical values, plays a key role in motivating dietary change. This chapter examines how to strengthen these drivers, while addressing common gaps in awareness or misconceptions that may act as barriers to healthier and more sustainable eating.

DRIVERS

- Health and/or environmental awareness
- Health consciousness
- **Animal welfare**

TECHNIQUES

Strategy

Actions and selected examples

01. Commitment

Group

Cooking

"Meat-Free Monday": Schools and workplaces of the city encourage participants to commit publicly. (e.g., social media posts, in-app pledges)

02. Mental rehearsal of successful performance

Personal

Mindfulness

Taking a moment to remind yourself of the goals you have already accomplished regarding healthy and sustainable diets.

03. Identity associated with changed behavior

Group

Social media

Joining a Facebook group for mothers who share kid friendly, healthy recipes.

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SKILLS, FACILITIES AND CONFIDENCE

Confidence and practical skills in preparing healthy and sustainable foods are essential enablers of dietary change. This chapter focuses on how cooking abilities, access to appropriate facilities, and perceived competence influence food behaviors, and provides guidance on techniques to build these skills and capacities.

DRIVERS

- Ability and confidence to prepare H&S foods

TECHNIQUES

Strategy

Actions and selected examples

01. Reduce negative emotions (1)

Personal | App, Communication campaign

Motivational posters in supermarkets. Certain apps like "Inspirational Quotes Wallpaper", "Motivational Daily Quotes", "Inspirational Quotes Daily".

02. Problem solving

Group | Cooking workshops

Interactive cooking workshops (example: how to cook on a budget?), community initiatives for people who are facing similar obstacles.

03. Behavioral practice/ rehearsal

Group | Educational moment

Educational simulations: virtual or physical roleplays where participants practice to make healthy choices in a restaurant and learn how to say 'no' to a dessert.

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04. Graded tasks

Group

Rewards, Cooking

Participate in a cooking class. Your teacher will give you a grade on your dish.

05. Verbal persuasion about capability (3)

Personal

Communication campaign

EFSA (European Food Safety Authority) promotes healthy food and they have initiatives that state that everyone can cook healthy meals.

06. Information about Social & Environmental Consequences (2)

Personal

Communication campaign, App

Campagne #Safe2EatEU, Initiative "Generation awake", apps like "Frigo Magic".

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SKILLS, FACILITIES AND CONFIDENCE

DRIVERS

• Cooking skills

BARRIERS

• Limited cooking skills

TECHNIQUES

Strategy

Actions and selected examples

01. Behavioral practice/
rehearsal

Group

Social media

Practice makes perfect: The more you cook, the better you become at cooking.

02. Demonstration of
the behavior

Personal

Social media, Video

Using social media: watching tutorials, online recipes, having influencer film themselves while eating a nutritious meal.

03. Instruction on how
to perform the behavior

Personal

Social media, Video

Practice makes perfect: The more you cook, the better you become at cooking.

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04. Problem solving

Personal | Communication campaign

If there is a specific problem, you can always look on the internet or YouTube and see how you can fix it. You can also join a cooking class and ask your specific problem there.

05. Generalization of target behavior (1)

Personal | Cooking, Educational moment

If you are doing well with slicing an onion, try other vegetables and see how that turns out. If you can make an omelet, try a pancake later. If you can follow a recipe, try to be creative with it to make it something new. You can also learn how to read food labels, if you learn how to read things like fats (saturated vs unsaturated), you can try these skills on other foods.

06. Reward (outcome)(2)

Personal | Rewards

Challenges and competitions, if you win a competition, you can win workshops or discounts on cooking tools.

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TIME AVAILABILITY

Time availability is a critical determinant of food choice, often acting as a barrier to the adoption of healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns. This chapter explores strategies to help individuals and communities overcome time-related obstacles and integrate better food practices into busy daily routines.

BARRIERS

- Lack of time/time constraints
- Irregular working hours
- Preparation time

TECHNIQUES

Strategy

Actions and selected examples

01. Planning week menu

Personal Cooking, App, List

In the weekend you can make a planning for the following week. That way, you know exactly when and what to cook and make this fit into your schedule. Example: On Monday you have a hobby after work, so you don't have a lot of time afterwards to cook. On Monday you can then make wraps à the only "cooking" part will be grilling some fish or meat, and the rest will be raw vegetables from the fridge. There you go, a recipe that takes 10 minutes maximum. Apps like Meallme and Yazo can help you with your meal planning. Meal prepping : On a day where you have more time (maybe weekend?), you can make meals for the week that follows. This means making a very large portion, that you can divide into 4 smaller meals for example. If you do this, you only have to cook once or twice a week.

02. Make shopping lists

Personal App, List

Never go shopping without a list, you will be overwhelmed in supermarkets. If you clearly know what to bring home, shopping will be much faster. You can use the app "Bring".

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ATTITUDE AND BELIEFS

Personal attitudes and beliefs about diet strongly shape food behaviors. This chapter examines common cognitive and emotional factors - including the belief that one's current diet is already good - that can either support or hinder positive dietary change. Practical strategies are provided to align attitudes and beliefs with healthy and sustainable eating goals.

BARRIERS

- Beliefs that one's diet is good/healthy

TECHNIQUES

Strategy

Actions and selected examples

01. Credible source

Personal Website, Skills

Promoting use of official websites of the country (e.g. Gezond Leven In Belgium). It offers science-based resources and tips to help individuals make healthy eating choices. The site covers a wide range of topics, including heart health, high blood pressure, exercise, and nutrition tips for different life stages. Collaborations with celebrity chefs.

02. Information about health consequences

Group Social media, Skills

Collaborations with influencers on social media who share information about the health benefits of common foods and spices we use.

03. Information about emotional consequences

Group Social media, Skills

Starting a TV program where there is storytelling from people who made a lifestyle change and talk about how this influenced their emotional and physical state. This can also happen on social media.

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04. Comparative imagining of future outcomes (1)

Personal

Skills, Communication campaign

A campaign that spreads awareness about high **blood pressure showing twins: one person lives a healthy lifestyle and grows old, the other twin experiences a range of complications.**

05. Information about Social & Environmental Consequences

Personal

Skills, Video

A documentary about the meat industry and the **devastating effects on climate change.**

06. Pros & Cons (2)

Personal

List

A list of the pros and cons of having an indulgent lifestyle.

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CULTURAL AND SOCIAL NORMS

Cultural and social norms deeply influence eating behaviors by shaping perceptions of what is acceptable, desirable, or valued in food choices. This chapter explores how to leverage positive cultural drivers while addressing cultural or social barriers that may impede healthier and more sustainable diets.

DRIVERS

- Cultural influences

BARRIERS

- Cultural influences

TECHNIQUES

Strategy

Actions and selected examples

01. Using characteristics of the target group in source, message, and channel leads to more positive reception of the message (4)

Personal

Communication campaign

"5 A Day" campaign in the UK, which encourages people to eat at least five portions of fruits and vegetables each day. For children, the campaign uses fun and engaging messages, such as "Eat a Rainbow" to encourage them to try different colored fruits and vegetables.

02. Social Comparison(2)

Personal

Communication campaign

Campaigns showing individuals eating healthy, so that the target group compares their eating behaviour and adapts their normative perceptions **(perceives the norm to be eating healthy foods).**

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FAMILY AND SOCIAL SUPPORT

Social support from family, peers, and community networks is a powerful driver of dietary behavior. Conversely, a lack of support can represent a significant barrier. This chapter highlights how to foster supportive environments and engage social networks to facilitate sustainable dietary change.

DRIVERS

- Family and social support

BARRIERS

- Lack of social support

TECHNIQUES

Strategy

Actions and selected examples

01. Social support (practical)

Group

Social media, Cooking workshops

A cooking workshop for the parent and their child. The workshop aims to create an environment where the children are engaging in the process of making a healthy meal, while the parents can set a good example by guiding them through the process. Social support groups (Facebook or other platforms) in which there is a 'leader' promoting healthy food changes and encouraging people.

02. Restructuring the social environment

Group

Communication campaign

The "Healthy Food for All" initiative by the World Health Organization (WHO) aims to create healthier food environments and promote social support networks to encourage healthier eating habits. The campaign involves local communities in creating and maintaining community gardens, farmers' markets, and healthy food co-ops. This helps to increase access to fresh, nutritious food

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03. Monitoring of behavior by others without feedback

Personal App, Diary

The **"Healthy Eating Index (HEI) Challenge"** encourages participants to track their dietary habits and share their progress with a community of peers. Participants log their daily food intake using a mobile app or online platform. Participants join a community where they can see anonymized data from others. This creates a sense of accountability and social support without direct feedback.

04. Social comparison (1)

Group Social media, Rewards

The **"Blue Zones Project"** aims to transform communities by promoting healthier lifestyles, including better eating habits, through social comparison and community support. The initiative includes friendly competitions and challenges, such as **"walking school buses"** for children or workplace wellness challenges. These activities encourage participants to compare their progress with others and strive to improve.

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WILLPOWER

Individual willpower and self-regulation capacities can determine the success of dietary change efforts, particularly when facing temptation or ingrained habits. This chapter presents practical techniques to strengthen willpower, enhance self-control, and support the maintenance of healthier and more sustainable eating behaviors over time.

DRIVERS

· Willpower

BARRIERS

· Lack of willpower

TECHNIQUES

Strategy

Actions and selected examples

01. Mental rehearsal of successful performance

Personal

Communication campaign

"Food Smart Cities" (EU Sustainable Food Program) promotes mindful eating and meal planning, it encourages to mentally rehearse meal preparation, reducing impulsive unhealthy eating. **#TasteTheFuture** (EU Green Deal), promotes reducing food waste, it uses mental rehearsal techniques to help consumers picture themselves meal-prepping efficiently.

02. Pros and cons

Personal

List, Pros and cons list

Imagine the feeling if you ignore health and choose an unhealthy option. You'll feel terrible. So before making the choice, list some pros and cons of the choice you're about to make. In supermarkets there can be flyers, listing the pros and cons of saturated fats for example.

03. Identity with changed behavior

Personal

Mindfulness, Habits

Identify yourself with who you want to become. You can practice saying "I am a healthy eater" and then you will act like one. Use public figures as an example and gain some inspiration.

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04. Self- incentive (1)

Personal

Rewards

Promise yourself some good things after the healthy behavior. For example, if you eat balanced the whole week, you can watch your favorite movie during the weekend.

05. Information about Social & Environmental Consequences

Personal

Graph, Communication campaign

#Safe2EatEU Campaign. Hang up some facts in supermarkets such as "Did you know that eating no meat for just one day a week saves as much CO₂ as driving 1,250 km less?" "By choosing plant-based options more often, you support sustainable farmers and help reduce child labor in the livestock industry.

06. Incentive (outcome) (2)

Personal

Graph

If you set a goal of eating 2 pieces of fruit every day and you don't do it, you pay \$10 to a friend or put it in a jar for every piece of fruit you missed. You don't want to lose money, so you're more likely to eat that fruit.

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CULTURAL FOOD PRACTICES/ CULTURAL IDENTITY

Food practices linked to cultural identity and traditions are central to how people eat. These cultural drivers can either facilitate or hinder healthier and more sustainable choices. This chapter discusses ways to align interventions with cultural contexts, ensuring that dietary change efforts are respectful, relevant, and effective.

DRIVERS

- Cultural traditions/ eating culture
- **Religion**

BARRIERS

- **Cultural Influences**

TECHNIQUES

Strategy

Actions and selected examples

01. Using characteristics of the target group in source, message, and channel à leads to more positive reception of the message (5)

Personal TV

A cooking show that reaches Moroccan families, the recipes include traditional dishes while also focusing on the nutritional value.

02. Information about Other's Approval

Group Communication

"Healthy Halal Choices" program. This program aims to encourage Muslim communities to make healthier food choices by emphasizing the alignment of healthy eating with Islamic dietary laws.

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